

REMAPPING AND COMMUNAL CONFLICTS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Esara, Umoh Victor¹

Asuquo, Mfon Effiong²

Samuel, Mercy Emmanuel¹

¹Department of Sociology and Anthropology

University of Uyo, Uyo

Umohesar1@gmail.com

+2348060111898

mercysamuel081@gmail.com

07066631617

²Department of Sociology and Anthropology

Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

mfonasuquo@aksu.edu.ng

07035490011

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effects of the current remapping of Akwa Ibom State following the Akwa Ibom State Map Establishment Law 2023 passed by the State House of Assembly. Remapping has brought serious tension and boundary conflicts in the state, this situation has destroyed the age-long relationship that had existed between these communities. Survey design was used in this study with primary data collected through interview and participant Observation, while secondary data were extracted from extant literature. The study adopts Frustration - Aggression Theory to explain the phenomenon of communal conflict in Akwa Ibom state. Data were collected through interview, participants' observations and key informant interview. Data were analysed with excerpts from study participants. Study participants were selected using multiple sampling techniques from the three senatorial districts of the state. Findings of the study show that remapping has contributed to communal conflicts in the state. The prevalent cases of communal conflicts are a result of remapping and other contributory factors as well as, its effects on the residents of the affected Communities. The researchers recommended that the Akwa Ibom State government should resolve and find a lasting solution to communal conflicts by implementing the recommendations of commissions and panels of inquiry.

KEYWORD: Remapping, Conflict, Governance, Tension, Insecurity

INTRODUCTION

Remapping has brought about serious cases of communal conflicts in the state. As a result of remapping the State, some communities are now in a state of lawlessness and

senseless killings resulting from communal conflicts is becoming more alarming. This situation has created insecurity in the state, lives of innocent people are being taken on the slightest provocation and it is becoming more alarming across the warring communities. Some leaders in the affected communities alleged that the former "Governor of Akwa Ibom State, Udom Emmanuel brought the political sentiment of remapping to give his Local Government Area, Onna access to the Atlantic coastline to be eligible as a host Community under the petroleum industry ACT (PIA). This is an indication that leaders are capable of complicating social order in communities (Peters and Bassey, 2019)

The Ijaw community leaders in the state as recently as last year at a meeting made it clear that they would not cede any part of their ancestral land and urged the state government to drop the idea. Prof. Benjamin Okaba, President of Pan-Ijaw socio-cultural and pressure group, Ijaw National Congress (INC) last year appealed to the federal government to wade in the boundary crisis occasioned by the recent moves by Akwa Ibom State government to adjust boundaries of communities in the state. The group also appealed to the Chief of Defence Staff to check and caution against the recent invasion of Eastern Obollo Communities by Army and Navy troops at the instance of Akwa Ibom State government. The explained that the call followed reports of massive deployment of armed security operatives to intimidate communities who opposed to remapping the state which can lead to neglect of the people of the area (Usoro and Peters, 2019).

Prof. Benjamin Okaba, President of Ijaw National Congress who spoke in an interview session in Yenogoa, said that mapping and boundary adjustment are on the exclusive legislative list of federal government and therefore not the responsibility of Akwa Ibom State government. He alleged that there were already reports of avoidable communal conflicts orchestrated due to operations of Sterling Oil, a firm the former State governor has interest in, to justify the use of crude force to adjust the boundaries of various communities in the state. The President of Ijaw Nation Congress explained that Eastern Obollo, Ibeno and Oron communities as peaceful law abiding citizens had sought and got legal address in the favour, but regretted that Ijaws were being provoked to violence to pave way to occupation of the affected communities in the state.

Mr. Ini Ememobong, the Commissioner for Information in Akwa Ibom State, said in a telephone that he was not aware of the court judgement on the remapping. He that we are aware that the matter in question is surrounded by a lot of sentiment, but when sentiments are put aside, the issues become a lot simpler. The matter was passed through the State Assembly where representatives of the communities passed a bill to back the mapping and anyone who feels aggrieved can approach the court to seek address. He said that the state has powers to do what it is doing and, please take note, that we are talking about internal boundaries within the state; we are not tampering with interstate boundaries here, Ememobong said (Punch, May 13, 2023).

Some communities are against remapping, others see it as a welcome development in the state that would end the lingering communal conflicts in the state. The Paramount Ruler of Eket Local Government Area, Edidem Etim Abia, has said that unity and peaceful co-existence would be engendered following the Akwa Ibom State Map Establishment Laws 2023 passed by the State House of Assembly. Speaking in an interview in his palace, the monarch noted that the state's map was important as it would bring an end to years of disputes

over boundaries between neighbouring communities in the state. The Monarch said that we couldn't have continued as a state without having a map, an official gazetted map. What was circulated in the past was not an official map, it was something someone drew and people used it and that Map created a lot of problems, he said.

The Monarch commended Governor Udom Emmanuel for his courage and determination in ensuring that the state had an official map, which he described as a vital tool for ensuring peace and stability in the state. He said that the map is expected to show clearly where the boundary of each Local Government is and bring to an end all communal conflicts in the state, the Governor has done well, he has the courage to do the right thing and not mind anybody, we couldn't have had a state that didn't have a map, he said (Punch, April 20th, 2023). The Monarch also drew attention to the fact that the map would prevent Local Government Areas from making claims on territories that were not rightfully theirs. He said that the people of Eket have been fighting since 1914 to get the proper boundary demarcation between Eket and Ibeno. This case went up to the privy council, the highest court in the British Empire and right from Nigeria, Eket won the case both in the High Court of Appeal to the British Council, but Ibeno never accepted that judgement (Onwudiwe, 2004).

The monarch said it is not up to Ibeno to implement the judgement, but when there is judgement that involves land, it is the government that should implement the judgement. But successive Government haven't implement the judgement. He said they also joined in the case to argue where QIT (Qua Iboe Terminal) is and they lost, the appeal was thrown out, but still they won't give up. This map is very important, not just for Eket alone because it affected Onna, Mkpato Enin, Easter Obolo and Ikot Abasi. But this map is expected to show clearly where the boundary of each Local Government is and bring to an end all the communal conflicts, he further noted that in the past, there had been communal conflicts over terrorists that were not properly delineated, leading to tension and sometimes communal conflicts between communities in the State.

Four killed in renewed Akwa Ibom State communal conflicts, Akwa Ibom State Police Command has confirmed the death of four persons in the renewed communal conflict between the Amazaba Community in Eastern Obolo and their Ikot Akpan Udo neighbours in the Ikot Abasi Local Government Area of the State. This is because it has deployed a tactical force of about 300 officers to the warring communities to dominate and quell the disturbances. The Command's Public Relations Officer, Odivo Macdon, who disclosed this while speaking with newsmen on Saturday said that Commissioner of Police, Olatoye Durusinmi said that normally would return in the area, he appealed to relevant state and non-state actors to intensify their interface to resolve the crisis. The PUNCH reports that the Amazaba and Eastern Obolo crisis earlier broke out in 2008, resulting in the wanton destruction of lives and property and the displacement of thousands of residents from the warring communities. Since then efforts by successive administrations to resolve the crises have yielded little or no results. Governor Udom Emmanuel's efforts to resolve the age-long communal conflict and resettle the displaced persons by constituting a white paper complementation committee headed by the Commissioner of Health, Prof. Augustine Umoh, had suffered several setbacks following occasional disruptions of the peace initiatives by the warring communities. However, communal conflicts are very destructive because it hinder peace and security in the affected area. Thus, effective strategies that can help to nip Communal conflicts in the bud and prevent

it from escalating if it erupt, as well as to sustain peace to avert future occurrences and the attendant large scale should be developed by any affected areas, Community, state or even the nation that seen peace, growth and development (Oboh, 2006).

Communal conflicts have become common phenomenon in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria in general. These conflicts are mostly ethnic and some are as a result over the struggle for land and other natural resources. Quite several studies have been undertaken by researchers on communal conflicts, focusing on its different dimensions. This becomes imperative to situate this study in a proper context and also to establish a link between the existing or previous studies and this research work to identify knowledge gaps in the literature concerning the focus of this study. The essence of this is to shed more light on where to intervene by providing updates and contributing to the missing link and to the existing body of knowledge in the field.

The rate at which communal conflicts escalate in Akwa Ibom State is quite disturbing and more worrisome as communities and local government areas have occupied a volatile position in the State. It is important to note that those warring communities contribute to insecurity in the state because arms and ammunitions acquire to fight communal wars are being used for armed robbery, cultism, thuggery, Kidnapping and bunker. After remapping the state, we continued to witness vicious cycle of violent conflicts, some of which have attracted national attention. Issues that do not warrant people engaging in killing and destruction of property have surfaced with devastating consequence to individuals and communities as many have be totally dislodge from the ancestral home town. One keep wondering what could be the possible causes of the communal conflicts in Akwa Ibom State as a whole immediately after remapping, with reference to Ikot Abasi and Eastern Obolo, Eket and Ibeno, Uruan and Okobo amongst others. The major objective of this study is to examine how remapping contribute to communal conflicts and insecurity in the State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The word conflict is taken from the Latin word "Conflictus" meaning "Struck together". Conflict means clash, contention, confrontation, battle or struggle, controversy or quarrel (Nwolise, 1997). Conflict as an element of social interactions has evoked a lot of arguments. Suffice it to say that there are many definitions of Conflict. Coser (1956) defined Conflict as a struggle over value and claims over status, power and resources, in which the opponents aim to neutralize, injure or eliminate their rivals. Donovhue and Kolt (1992), said that conflict has to do with the expression of differences by interdependent people in the course of achieving their goals and needs. Bassey (2002) contended that conflict arises as a result of incompatible or mutually exclusive goals aims or values espoused by human beings. This definition sees conflict from a goal perspective.

Omosho (2004) avers that it is widely believed by scholars that a conflict situation crops up when two or more parties cannot agree on an issue. The parties involved may not necessarily be the government. Posits that "the term conflicts embodies the notion of strife, struggle, differences and disagreement. It is indeed the struggle for mutually exclusive rewards or the use of incompatible means to achieve a goal. Horowitz (1985) sees conflicts as a "Struggle in which the aim to get objective and simultaneously neutralize or eliminate rivals". Daugharly and Falzgart cited in Omotosho (2004), view conflict as a situation in

which one identifiable group the human being which could be tribal, ethnic, cultural, linguistic, religious, socio-economic, political or otherwise is in a state of conscious opposition to one or more other identifiable human groups. This could be because those groups are pursuing what appears to be incompatible goals (Akpaeti, 2005).

However, Pruitt and Rubin (1986) see conflict from perceptual point of view (cited in Bassey, 2002). To them conflict denotes the perceived divergence of interest(s), or aspirations that cannot be achieved simultaneously. Ross (1993:14) notes that conflict "occurs when parties disagree about the distribution of material or symbolic resources and act because of the incompatibility of goals or a perceived divergence of interest." It has also been noted that conflict arises as a consequence of the striving of a man the social being who in the course of promoting some of his objectives, either intentionally or unintentionally upsets or directs to negative uses, instead of strengthening along beneficial line, some of the arrangement ought to be for the benefit of man hence, conflicts come up as a result of negative contradiction and are such irresolvable by peaceful means (Igwe, 1997; Nwawegbo, 2005).

Communal Conflicts: Communal conflicts arise over the production and consumption of goods, socialization, social control, and social participation (Warren, 1978:99). Communal conflicts are therefore products of social relations. Communal conflicts are threat or action of one party directed at territory, right, interests or privileges of another party, because of differences over economic issues, power of authority, cultural values and beliefs (Robinson, 1989; Coleman, 1957). It has been posited in the literature that most communal conflicts are mainly economic issues of which land constitute about 90% of it (Oтите and Albert, 1999). The thesis then is "if community is place where people interact to meet the daily needs, then communal conflict takes place within a geographical area and elates people's interaction.

Remapping: Remapping refers to redesigning by adjusting it from where it was before and making it new.

Insecurity: Insecurity refers to a state of chaos, disorder and conflict where lives and property are not guaranteed safety (Esara, 2014).

Causes of Communal Conflicts

Various factors have been identified by scholars as responsible for communal conflicts in the country. The causes vary from one area to another. Yecho (2006) indicated that the causes of communal conflicts are not static, but rather dynamic and varied in nature depending on the socio-economic and geopolitical circumstances of the time. Onwudiwe (2004) listed social conditions as population explosion, economic migration and the anti-poor policies of the government as triggers of communal friction. However, Horowitz (2000) pinned down communal conflicts to revolve around politics, politicians, and their pursuit of group advantage. Identified indigene/settler problem, religious differences, ownership of land and its resources, goals and aspirations of people as some of the factors that can ignite communal conflict in the country. Hembe (2000) indicated that political struggle and colonization, while Lyam (2006) mentioned loss of soil fertility, soil erosion, deforestation, bush burning and flooding as some of the causes of communal conflict. Yecho (2006) pointed out that the fundamental causes of communal conflicts are poor economic conditions, high level of illiteracy, the quest for and fear of domination by other groups, land disputes, marked ownership, chieftaincy tussle and party politics.

Varvar (2000) indicated that increased demand for land for agriculture, unemployment, rural hunger, poverty impoverishment as communal conflict triggers. Deprivation, exploitation and domination of minority groups by major ethnic groups and leadership problem where highlighted by Angya and Doki (2006) as factors that can exert communal conflict. Equally, religious differences, competition for livelihood resources and traditional Chieftaincy tussles were enumerated by Oboh and Hyande (2006) as potential communal conflict triggers in the country. In analyzing communal conflict one can definitely say that the following are principally the causes of communal conflict.

Land Factor: Land is taken in this study to mean an important economic asset and a source of livelihood, and it also closely linked to the identity, history and cultural belief of communities. Land, understood from this perspective, explains why communities therefore can readily mobilize around land related issues, making it a central object of conflict having been ceded from one community and given to another as a result of remapping.

Economic Factor: This factor manifests in the forms of competition for inadequate resources such as land and its content; problems of distribution of available resources, unemployment and poverty.

Social Factor: This has to do with issues that border on deprivation, envy, jealousy, marginalisation and exploitation of people. Fear of domination by major groups is equally a social factor that attracts communal conflicts.

Political Factor: It involves the contest for available political positions in a community and leadership failure. Also added to this, is traditional chieftaincy tussle imminent in various communities across the country. Youths who are agents of community development (Peters *et al*, 2023) are sometimes used for political thugery and conflicts.

Food Insecurity Factor: Food and nutrition insecurity becoming increasingly concentrated in conflict-affected communities, affecting millions of people. Policies and interventions that build resilience to these shocks have the power to limit the breadth and depth of communal conflicts.

Population Explosion: As population increases, people need land for building and other economic purposes, making land a scarce resource that communities struggle over ownership.

Unemployment: According to Okafor (2011) unemployment in Nigeria has attendant social, economic, political and psychological consequences. One of its social consequences on the Nigerian youths is the high level of youth Unemployment. A Phenomenon which encourages the development of Street youths and urban urchins "area boys" who grow up in a culture that encourages criminal behaviour and insecurity.

Frequent Interference in Chieftaincy Affairs by Government: The frequent interference in Chieftaincy affairs takes place through appointment, demotion, deposition and banishment. As a result of this interference, there have also been several communal conflicts between state governors and traditional rulers leaving a trail of heightened tension in many local government areas. The persistent communal conflicts in Akwa Ibom State have increased the level of poverty as lives and property are destroyed thereby affecting the economy of the state.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Frustration-Aggression Theory was adopted to explain the study. This theory was propounded by Dollard, Neal E. Miller et al in 1939 and has been expanded and modified by

scholars like Lenard Bekowitz (1962) and Aubrey Yates (1962).

The thrust of this theory is that aggression is the result of frustration (IEC, 2010;1). Frustration can be viewed as a state that sets in if a goal-oriented act is delayed or not realized. Under frustrating condition or circumstances, aggressive behaviour is activated or stimulated to the extent of the situations that inhibit the attainment of the individual's or group's goal. Frustration-Aggression Theory is anchored on two postulates

- i. That aggressive behaviour requires the existence of frustration, and
- ii. That the existence of frustration stemming from social situations is a common cause of aggression.

For instance, within Nigerian societies, particularly Akwa Ibom State under Study, and is an important economic resource in the life of the people. Remapping has ceded land from one community to another, and that frustration triggered communal conflicts in the state. When two rival communities lay claims to ownership of a piece of land, and they prevent each other from having access to re, definitely the frustration of those communities would turn to anger and possibly, aggression against themselves, this resulted in the destruction of lives and property, it has also contributed to a high level of insecurity in the state.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for the study was a survey design. The survey allows a researcher to study the opinions, attitudes, and orientations of people in large population settings. The study area is Akwa Ibom state. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria, created on the 23rd of September 1987, with Uyo as its capital. Akwa Ibom is one of Nigeria's 36 states, with a population of over seven million people (aks.gov.ng 2024). The state was created from the former Cross River State and is currently the highest oil- and gas-producing state in the country. The state's capital is Uyo, with over 500,000 inhabitants. It is located in the coastal southern part of the country, lying between latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E. The state is located in the Sout-South geopolitical zone, and is bordered on the east by Cross River State, on the west by River State and Abia State, and on the south by the Atlantic Ocean and the southernmost tip of Cross River State.

Respondents were selected using multiple stages stratified sampling techniques. First, the state was stratified into three in accordance to the three senatorial districts of Uyo Senatorial District, Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District and Eket Senatorial District. Then, one local government area was purposively selected from each of the senatorial district, from where communities were randomly selected and respondents were randomly selected for the study. Interviews were conducted on the subject matter of the study and data collected was analysed with excerpts from the study participants.

RESULT

The majority of the study participants in their responses to the interview said that state remapping is purely political just to make some community to benefit from oil at the detriment of the true owners of the land. Most of the interviewed participants across Eastern Obolo said that the people of Ikot Abasi and Onna are taking advantage by trespassing into Eastern Obolo's land because of state remapping. Study participants also envisage present and future communal conflicts because no portion of their land would be ceded to another community

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and this would result in serious bloodshed.

One of the study participants from Onna Local Government Area narrates:

State remapping is a welcome development in Akwa Ibom State because it would bring a lasting solution to all lingering communal conflicts in the state. He said that all the boundaries between the warring communities would be properly demarcated to forestall future communal conflicts in the state, (interviewed on 9-05-2023).

Most of the study participants interviewed by the researchers narrated their loss as a result of state remapping. One of the study participants said that;

The people were living peacefully over the years until recently when the state House of Assembly passed the law for remapping the state, which eventually brought about communal war between Ikot Abasi and Eastern Obolo where lives and property worth several millions of naira were destroyed before the intervention of the state government, (interviewed 10-05-2023).

The state Commissioner for Information, Mr. Ini Emeobong in a telephone interview:

Mr. Ini Emeobong said that he was not aware of the court judgment that stop remapping. He said that we are aware that the matter in question is surrounded by a lot of sentiments, but when sentiments are put aside, the said issues become simpler. He said that the state has the powers to do what it is doing. He said communities and anyone who feels aggrieved can approach the court to seek redness, (interviewed on 13-05-2023).

Speaking in an interview in his palace, one of the monarchs as a key informant noted that;

The state's map was important as it would bring an end to years of disputes over boundaries between neighbouring communities in the state, (interviewed 02-4-2023).

The researchers observed that while some communities are against remapping, others see it as a welcome development in the state, saying that it would end the lingering communal conflicts in the state. The researcher observed that all the people that flee from their communities for fear of attack had return back home and continue with their legitimate business.

The study participants from Esit Eket and Ibeno Local Government Areas have pointed out that unity and peaceful co-existence would be engendered following the Akwa Ibom State Map Establishment Law 2023 passed by the State House of Assembly.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study has shown that remapping has ceded land from one community to another causing communal conflicts in the state. The study has shown that the Cause of communal conflict is a result of struggle over land and natural resources and these led to destruction of lives and property. The study further shows that communal conflicts has affected economic activities in the affected areas and has posted contributed to insecurity in the state. The study shows that Akwa Ibom State Government has spent millions of naira to deploy security personnel to restore law and order in the affected area. The study has shown that arms and ammunitions acquire during communal conflicts are usually used in kidnapping, armed robbery, bunkery business and thuggery all these contributes to insecurity in the state. The study shows that youths in the warring communities usually engage in selling of human parts and selling of hard drugs because the affected communities at this point is in a state of lawlessness. The study shares that remapping has triggered several communal conflicts in the state and this has destroyed the age-long peace and relationship enjoyed by the affected communities in the state.

The study shows that most of these communal conflicts are politically sponsored of the detriment of the poor masses and for the benefit of the politicians. The Study shows that government can end communal conflicts in the state by granting amnesty to youths of the affected communities and also retrieving arms and ammunitions from them for the safety of the future. The study reveal that there are cases of jungle justice within the warring communities because people are killed at the slightest provocation. The study also shows that there are cases of cultism in the affected communities as their youths are recruited as political things.

CONCLUSION

The study has established that remapping has contributed to communal conflicts in the state. The prevalent cases of communal conflicts are a result of remapping and other contributory factors as well as, its effects on the residents of the affected Communities. As earlier stated, conflicts and crises are inevitable societal phenomena. Management of Communal Conflicts can stem down the tide of the impending effects of such conflicts or worsen them. Often, the usual way of using force to stop conflicts is only necessary as an emergent measure. The government should go beyond the use of force to bring lasting solutions and peace to communities facing communal conflicts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For better resolution of communal conflicts in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria in general, the findings of this study have given rise to the following recommendations:

- i. The government should enforce laws on land and provide employment opportunities for the youths.
- ii. The government should grant amnesty to youths of the affected communities to withdraw arms and ammunition from them for the safety of the future.
- iii. Those who lost family members and properties in the communal conflicts should be compensated.
- iv. Professional conflict mediators should be engaged to find out the immediate and

remote cause of conflicts and send recommendations that would bring lasting peace in the area.

- v. Government should fake over all disputed land in the affected communities to serve as deterrence to others.

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